

DAG development for salutogenic outcome – Healthy newborn

ESC-DAGs Decision Log

	<u>Variables</u>
Outcome	Healthy newborn
Exposure(s)	Staffing exposure (One-to-one care during labour / vs. not one-to-one care during labour)
Control(s)	Gestational age Risk of hypoglycaemia Parity Mode of birth Maternal age Country of birth / ethnicity Pregnancy complications Birth weight Labour complications
Mediator(s)	Feeding method (Breastfeeding / Bottle) Risk of hypothermia Risk of Hyperbilirubinaemia
Moderator(s)	Cold season Time of birth

	<u>Diagrams</u>
IG Code (Figure 1)	<pre> dag { bb="0,0,1,1" "Birth weight" [pos="0.267,0.337"] "Blood type" [latent,pos="0.664,0.742"] "Breastfeeding initiation within 1 hour after birth" [latent,pos="0.687,0.266"] "Cold season" [pos="0.527,0.114"] "Cord pH" [latent,pos="0.665,0.176"] "Country of birth / ethnicity" [pos="0.332,0.535"] "Early skin to skin contact after birth" [latent,pos="0.842,0.322"] "Feeding method (Breastfeeding / Bottle)" [pos="0.642,0.529"] "Gestational age" [pos="0.255,0.215"] "Healthy Newborn" [outcome,pos="0.791,0.462"] "Labour complications" [pos="0.241,0.079"] "Maternal age" [pos="0.182,0.568"] "Maternal education" [latent,pos="0.788,0.571"] "Mode of birth" [pos="0.378,0.670"] "Neonatal haematoma" [latent,pos="0.570,0.758"] "Pregnancy complications" [pos="0.179,0.149"] "Risk of Hyperbilirubinaemia" [pos="0.598,0.626"] "Risk of hypoglycaemia" [pos="0.495,0.228"] "Risk of hypothermia" [pos="0.527,0.367"] "Staffing exposure (postnatal unit)" [exposure,pos="0.193,0.472"] "Time of birth" [pos="0.588,0.130"] "Weight loss" [latent,pos="0.713,0.638"] Apgar [latent,pos="0.595,0.229"] Parity [pos="0.296,0.653"] "Birth weight" -> "Risk of Hyperbilirubinaemia" "Birth weight" -> "Risk of hypoglycaemia" "Birth weight" -> "Risk of hypothermia" "Birth weight" -> "Staffing exposure (postnatal unit)" "Blood type" -> "Risk of Hyperbilirubinaemia" "Breastfeeding initiation within 1 hour after birth" -> "Feeding method (Breastfeeding / Bottle)" "Cold season" -> "Risk of hypothermia" "Cord pH" -> "Risk of hypoglycaemia" "Cord pH" -> "Risk of hypothermia" "Country of birth / ethnicity" -> "Risk of hypothermia" "Country of birth / ethnicity" -> "Staffing exposure (postnatal unit)" "Early skin to skin contact after birth" -> "Feeding method (Breastfeeding / Bottle)" "Early skin to skin contact after birth" -> "Risk of hypothermia" "Feeding method (Breastfeeding / Bottle)" -> "Risk of Hyperbilirubinaemia" "Feeding method (Breastfeeding / Bottle)" -> "Risk of hypoglycaemia" "Feeding method (Breastfeeding / Bottle)" -> "Risk of hypothermia" "Feeding method (Breastfeeding / Bottle)" -> "Staffing exposure (postnatal unit)" "Feeding method (Breastfeeding / Bottle)" -> "Weight loss" "Gestational age" -> "Birth weight" "Gestational age" -> "Risk of Hyperbilirubinaemia" "Gestational age" -> "Risk of hypoglycaemia" "Gestational age" -> "Risk of hypothermia" "Gestational age" -> "Staffing exposure (postnatal unit)" "Labour complications" -> "Risk of hypoglycaemia" "Labour complications" -> "Risk of hypothermia" "Labour complications" -> "Staffing exposure (postnatal unit)" </pre>

Reduced IG DAG (simplified,
Figure 2)

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"Maternal age" -> "Risk of hypothermia"
"Maternal age" -> "Staffing exposure (postnatal unit)"
"Maternal education" -> "Healthy Newborn"
"Mode of birth" -> "Neonatal haematoma"
"Mode of birth" -> "Risk of hypoglycaemia"
"Mode of birth" -> "Staffing exposure (postnatal unit)"
"Neonatal haematoma" -> "Risk of Hyperbilirubinaemia"
"Pregnancy complications" -> "Risk of hypoglycaemia"
"Pregnancy complications" -> "Staffing exposure (postnatal unit)"
"Risk of Hyperbilirubinaemia" -> "Healthy Newborn"
"Risk of hypoglycaemia" -> "Healthy Newborn"
"Risk of hypoglycaemia" -> "Staffing exposure (postnatal unit)"
"Risk of hypoglycaemia" <-> "Risk of hypothermia"
"Risk of hypothermia" -> "Healthy Newborn"
"Staffing exposure (postnatal unit)" -> "Healthy Newborn"
"Time of birth" -> "Risk of hypothermia"
"Weight loss" -> "Risk of Hyperbilirubinaemia"
Apgar -> "Risk of hypoglycaemia"
Apgar -> "Risk of hypothermia"
Parity -> "Risk of hypothermia"
Parity -> "Staffing exposure (postnatal unit)"
}
dag {
  bb="0,0,1,1"
  "Birth weight" [pos="0.354,0.376"]
  "Cold season" [pos="0.641,0.287"]
  "Country of birth / ethnicity" [pos="0.425,0.547"]
  "Feeding method (Breastfeeding / Bottle)" [pos="0.659,0.502"]
  "Gestational age" [pos="0.327,0.232"]
  "Healthy Newborn" [outcome,pos="0.791,0.462"]
  "Labour complications" [pos="0.317,0.150"]
  "Maternal age" [pos="0.229,0.559"]
  "Mode of birth" [pos="0.484,0.666"]
  "Pregnancy complications" [pos="0.225,0.112"]
  "Risk of Hyperbilirubinaemia" [pos="0.591,0.613"]
  "Risk of hypoglycaemia" [pos="0.579,0.112"]
  "Risk of hypothermia" [pos="0.492,0.353"]
  "Staffing exposure (postnatal unit)" [exposure,pos="0.193,0.472"]
  "Time of birth" [pos="0.672,0.358"]
  Parity [pos="0.297,0.614"]
  "Birth weight" -> "Risk of Hyperbilirubinaemia"
  "Birth weight" -> "Risk of hypoglycaemia"
  "Birth weight" -> "Risk of hypothermia"
  "Birth weight" -> "Staffing exposure (postnatal unit)"
  "Cold season" -> "Risk of hypothermia"
  "Country of birth / ethnicity" -> "Risk of hypothermia"
  "Country of birth / ethnicity" -> "Staffing exposure (postnatal unit)"
  "Feeding method (Breastfeeding / Bottle)" -> "Risk of Hyperbilirubinaemia"
  "Feeding method (Breastfeeding / Bottle)" -> "Risk of hypoglycaemia"
  "Feeding method (Breastfeeding / Bottle)" -> "Risk of hypothermia"
  "Feeding method (Breastfeeding / Bottle)" -> "Staffing exposure (postnatal unit)"
  "Gestational age" -> "Birth weight"
  "Gestational age" -> "Risk of Hyperbilirubinaemia"
  "Gestational age" -> "Risk of hypoglycaemia"
  "Gestational age" -> "Risk of hypothermia"
  "Gestational age" -> "Staffing exposure (postnatal unit)"
  "Labour complications" -> "Risk of hypoglycaemia"
  "Labour complications" -> "Risk of hypothermia"
  "Labour complications" -> "Staffing exposure (postnatal unit)"
  "Maternal age" -> "Risk of hypothermia"
  "Maternal age" -> "Staffing exposure (postnatal unit)"
  "Mode of birth" -> "Risk of Hyperbilirubinaemia"
  "Mode of birth" -> "Risk of hypoglycaemia"
  "Mode of birth" -> "Staffing exposure (postnatal unit)"
  "Pregnancy complications" -> "Risk of hypoglycaemia"
  "Pregnancy complications" -> "Staffing exposure (postnatal unit)"
  "Risk of Hyperbilirubinaemia" -> "Healthy Newborn"
  "Risk of hypoglycaemia" -> "Healthy Newborn"
  "Risk of hypoglycaemia" -> "Staffing exposure (postnatal unit)"
  "Risk of hypoglycaemia" <-> "Risk of hypothermia"
  "Risk of hypothermia" -> "Healthy Newborn"
  "Staffing exposure (postnatal unit)" -> "Healthy Newborn"
  "Time of birth" -> "Risk of hypothermia"
  Parity -> "Risk of hypothermia"
  Parity -> "Staffing exposure (postnatal unit)"
}

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DAG Code (adapted, Figure 3)

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dag {
  bb="0,0,1,1"
  "Birth weight" [pos="0.354,0.376"]
  "Cold season" [pos="0.641,0.287"]
  "Country of birth / ethnicity" [pos="0.425,0.547"]
  "Feeding method (Breastfeeding / Bottle)" [pos="0.659,0.502"]
  "Gestational age" [pos="0.327,0.232"]
  "Healthy Newborn" [outcome,pos="0.791,0.462"]
  "Labour complications" [pos="0.317,0.150"]
  "Maternal age" [pos="0.229,0.559"]
  "Mode of birth" [pos="0.484,0.666"]
  "Pregnancy complications" [pos="0.225,0.112"]
  "Risk of Hyperbilirubinaemia" [pos="0.591,0.613"]
  "Risk of hypoglycaemia" [pos="0.579,0.112"]
  "Risk of hypothermia" [pos="0.492,0.353"]
  "Staffing exposure (postnatal unit)" [exposure,pos="0.193,0.472"]
  "Time of birth" [pos="0.672,0.358"]
  Parity [pos="0.297,0.614"]
  "Birth weight" -> "Risk of Hyperbilirubinaemia"
}

```


**Adjustment set and adjusted
DAG (Figure 4)**

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"Birth weight" -> "Risk of hypoglycaemia"
"Birth weight" -> "Risk of hypothermia"
"Birth weight" -> "Staffing exposure (postnatal unit)"
"Cold season" -> "Risk of hypothermia"
"Country of birth / ethnicity" -> "Risk of hypothermia"
"Country of birth / ethnicity" -> "Staffing exposure (postnatal unit)"
"Feeding method (Breastfeeding / Bottle)" -> "Risk of Hyperbilirubinaemia"
"Feeding method (Breastfeeding / Bottle)" -> "Risk of hypothermia"
"Feeding method (Breastfeeding / Bottle)" -> "Staffing exposure (postnatal unit)"
"Gestational age" -> "Birth weight"
"Gestational age" -> "Risk of Hyperbilirubinaemia"
"Gestational age" -> "Risk of hypoglycaemia"
"Gestational age" -> "Risk of hypothermia"
"Gestational age" -> "Staffing exposure (postnatal unit)"
"Labour complications" -> "Risk of hypoglycaemia"
"Labour complications" -> "Staffing exposure (postnatal unit)"
"Maternal age" -> "Risk of hypothermia"
"Maternal age" -> "Staffing exposure (postnatal unit)"
"Mode of birth" -> "Risk of Hyperbilirubinaemia"
"Mode of birth" -> "Risk of hypoglycaemia"
"Mode of birth" -> "Staffing exposure (postnatal unit)"
"Pregnancy complications" -> "Risk of hypoglycaemia"
"Pregnancy complications" -> "Staffing exposure (postnatal unit)"
"Risk of Hyperbilirubinaemia" -> "Healthy Newborn"
"Risk of hypoglycaemia" -> "Feeding method (Breastfeeding / Bottle)"
"Risk of hypoglycaemia" -> "Healthy Newborn"
"Risk of hypoglycaemia" -> "Staffing exposure (postnatal unit)"
"Risk of hypoglycaemia" <-> "Risk of hypothermia"
"Risk of hypothermia" -> "Healthy Newborn"
"Staffing exposure (postnatal unit)" -> "Healthy Newborn"
"Time of birth" -> "Risk of hypothermia"
Parity -> "Risk of hypothermia"
Parity -> "Staffing exposure (postnatal unit)"
}
dag {
bb="0,0,1,1"
"Birth weight" [adjusted,pos="0.354,0.376"]
"Cold season" [pos="0.641,0.287"]
"Country of birth / ethnicity" [adjusted,pos="0.425,0.547"]
"Feeding method (Breastfeeding / Bottle)" [adjusted,pos="0.659,0.502"]
"Gestational age" [adjusted,pos="0.327,0.232"]
"Healthy Newborn" [outcome,pos="0.791,0.462"]
"Labour complications" [adjusted,pos="0.317,0.150"]
"Maternal age" [adjusted,pos="0.229,0.559"]
"Mode of birth" [adjusted,pos="0.484,0.666"]
"Pregnancy complications" [adjusted,pos="0.225,0.112"]
"Risk of Hyperbilirubinaemia" [pos="0.591,0.613"]
"Risk of hypoglycaemia" [adjusted,pos="0.579,0.112"]
"Risk of hypothermia" [pos="0.492,0.353"]
"Staffing exposure (postnatal unit)" [exposure,pos="0.193,0.472"]
"Time of birth" [pos="0.672,0.358"]
Parity [adjusted,pos="0.297,0.614"]
"Birth weight" -> "Risk of Hyperbilirubinaemia"
"Birth weight" -> "Risk of hypoglycaemia"
"Birth weight" -> "Risk of hypothermia"
"Birth weight" -> "Staffing exposure (postnatal unit)"
"Cold season" -> "Risk of hypothermia"
"Country of birth / ethnicity" -> "Risk of hypothermia"
"Country of birth / ethnicity" -> "Staffing exposure (postnatal unit)"
"Feeding method (Breastfeeding / Bottle)" -> "Risk of Hyperbilirubinaemia"
"Feeding method (Breastfeeding / Bottle)" -> "Risk of hypothermia"
"Feeding method (Breastfeeding / Bottle)" -> "Staffing exposure (postnatal unit)"
"Gestational age" -> "Birth weight"
"Gestational age" -> "Risk of Hyperbilirubinaemia"
"Gestational age" -> "Risk of hypoglycaemia"
"Gestational age" -> "Risk of hypothermia"
"Gestational age" -> "Staffing exposure (postnatal unit)"
"Labour complications" -> "Risk of hypoglycaemia"
"Labour complications" -> "Staffing exposure (postnatal unit)"
"Maternal age" -> "Risk of hypothermia"
"Maternal age" -> "Staffing exposure (postnatal unit)"
"Mode of birth" -> "Risk of Hyperbilirubinaemia"
"Mode of birth" -> "Risk of hypoglycaemia"
"Mode of birth" -> "Staffing exposure (postnatal unit)"
"Pregnancy complications" -> "Risk of hypoglycaemia"
"Pregnancy complications" -> "Staffing exposure (postnatal unit)"
"Risk of Hyperbilirubinaemia" -> "Healthy Newborn"
"Risk of hypoglycaemia" -> "Feeding method (Breastfeeding / Bottle)"
"Risk of hypoglycaemia" -> "Healthy Newborn"
"Risk of hypoglycaemia" -> "Staffing exposure (postnatal unit)"
"Risk of hypoglycaemia" <-> "Risk of hypothermia"
"Risk of hypothermia" -> "Healthy Newborn"
"Staffing exposure (postnatal unit)" -> "Healthy Newborn"
"Time of birth" -> "Risk of hypothermia"
Parity -> "Risk of hypothermia"
Parity -> "Staffing exposure (postnatal unit)"
}

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Number of Edges assessed	36
Number of Edges reversed	1
Number of Edges retained	34
Number of Edges deleted	1

Figure 1 Integrated full DAG based on literature and expert knowledge, indicating unobserved variables

Figure 2 Integrated simplified DAG based on literature and expert knowledge, removed all unobserved variables (which are not confounding).

Figure 3 Adapted DAG after edge assessment.

Figure 4 Adapted DAG after edge assessment & adjusted for confounding variables [Risk of hypoglycaemia; Pregnancy complications; Labour complications; Gestational age; Birth weight; Country of birth/Ethnicity; Maternal age; Parity; Mode of birth; Feeding method].

IG Edges

Edge ID (#)	Variable From	Variable To	Decision	Theory and Reference
1 (page 7)	Staffing exposure (postnatal unit)	Healthy newborn	Retain	(1–4)
2 (page 9)	Pregnancy complications	Staffing exposure (postnatal unit)	Retain	(5,6)
3 (page 11)	Pregnancy complications	Risk of hypoglycaemia	Retain	(7–10)
4 (page 13)	Labour complications	Staffing exposure (postnatal unit)	Retain	(11,12)
5 (page 15)	Labour complications	Risk of hypoglycaemia	Retain	(13,14)
6 (page 15)	Labour complications	Risk of hypothermia	Delete	(15)
7 (page 18)	Gestational age	Staffing exposure (postnatal unit)	Retain	(16)
8 (page 20)	Gestational age	Birth weight	Retain	(17)
9 (page 21)	Gestational age	Risk of hyperbilirubinaemia	Retain	(18)
10 (page 23)	Gestational age	Risk of hypothermia	Retain	(19,20)
11 (page 24)	Birth weight	Staffing exposure (postnatal unit)	Retain	(21)
12 (page 26)	Birth weight	Risk of hypoglycaemia	Retain	(9,22,23)
13 (page 28)	Birth weight	Risk of hypothermia	Retain	(19–21)
14 (page 29)	Birth weight	Risk of hyperbilirubinaemia	Retain	(24)
15 (page 30)	Maternal age	Staffing exposure (postnatal unit)	Retain	(25)
16 (page 32)	Maternal age	Risk of hypothermia	Retain	(19,26)
17 (page 34)	Parity	Staffing exposure (postnatal unit)	Retain	(27–29)
18 (page 35)	Parity	Risk of hypothermia	Delete	(30)
19 (page 36)	Mode of birth	Staffing exposure (postnatal unit)	Retain	(31)
20 (page 38)	Mode of birth	Risk of hypoglycaemia	Retain	(7)
21 (page 39)	Mode of birth	Risk of hyperbilirubinaemia	Retain	(18)
22 (page 41)	Country of birth/ethnicity	Staffing exposure (postnatal unit)	Retain	(32,33)
23 (page 43)	Country of birth/ethnicity	Risk of hypothermia	Retain	(19)
24 (page 44)	Risk of hypoglycaemia	Staffing exposure (postnatal unit)	Retain	(1,4,34,35)
25 (page 46)	Risk of hypothermia	Risk of hypoglycaemia	Retain	(36–38)
26 (page 48)	Feeding method (Breastfeeding/Bottle)	Risk of hypoglycaemia	Reverse	(39)
27 (page 50)	Risk of hypoglycaemia	Healthy newborn	Retain	(36,40)
28 (page 51)	Cold season	Risk of hypothermia	Retain	(30,41)
29 (page 53)	Time of birth	Risk of hypothermia	Delete	(19)
30 (page 54)	Risk of hypothermia	Healthy newborn	Retain	(3)
31 (page 56)	Feeding method (Breastfeeding/Bottle)	Staffing exposure (postnatal unit)	Retain	(21)
32 (page 57)	Feeding method (Breastfeeding/Bottle)	Risk of hypothermia	Retain	(19)
33 (page 58)	Feeding method (Breastfeeding/Bottle)	Risk of hyperbilirubinaemia	Retain	(42,43)
34 (page 60)	Risk of hyperbilirubinaemia	Healthy newborn	Retain	(43)
35 (page 62)	Staffing exposure (postnatal unit)	Risk of hypothermia	Retain	(1,3)
36 (page 64)	Gestational age	Risk of hypoglycaemia	Retain	(44)

Translation

Edge ID (1)	Variable From	Variable To	Assessed Prior
Variable	Staffing exposure (postnatal unit)	Healthy newborn	No
Measurement	Proportion of target nurse-to-patient ratio during hospital stay on postnatal unit.	Measured bilirubin values, temperatures, glucose values from surveillance curve + Movement data for transfer	
	Question	Answer (Y/N)	Notes
Temporality	Hypothesised direction	Yes	Staffing levels on postnatal unit can influence health outcomes of newborns
	Reverse direction	No	
Face-validity	Hypothesised direction	Yes	It is plausible that high staffing levels contribute to better care and thus healthier newborns
	Reverse direction	No	
Recourse to theory	Hypothesised direction	Yes	Nurses were worried about bad outcomes for the baby due to less frequent assessments in the context of being too busy (1) Influence of midwife staffing on risk of hypoglycaemia in newborns not yet scrutinized. (4) Without appropriate intervention, progressive increase in hyperbilirubinemia places otherwise healthy babies at

			<p>risk of bilirubin-related brain damage. (2)</p> <p>Nursing interventions to achieve normal body temperature in newborns may include environmental temperature 23–25 °C, use of radiant warmers, exothermic mattresses, woollen or plastic caps, plastic wraps, humidified and heated gases (3). Those interventions cannot be ensured with low proportion of target nurse-to-patient ratio.</p>
	Reverse direction	No	
Counterfactual	Counterfactual exposure	Low vs. high proportion of target nurse-to-patient ratio during hospital stay on postnatal unit	
	Counterfactual question	What is the effect of low vs. high proportion of target nurse-to-patient ratio during hospital stay on postnatal unit on health outcomes of newborns?	
	Hypothesised outcome	We expect that higher nurse-to-patient ratios would be associated with better newborn health outcomes.	
	Further justification or suggested mechanism	High staffing levels enhance thorough monitoring of temperature, glucose	

			and bilirubin and prompt reaction in case of abnormalities which contribute to newborn's health	
	Reverse counterfactual exposure	NA		
	Reverse counterfactual question	NA		
	Reverse hypothesized outcome	NA		
	Further justification or suggested mechanism	NA		
	Conclusion	Retain		

Edge ID (2)	Variable From	Variable To	Assessed Prior
Variable	Pregnancy complications	Staffing exposure (postnatal unit)	Yes – IG DAG Breastfeeding
Measurement	ICD Diagnoses, if at least one is present, it is a yes	Proportion of target nurse-to-patient ratio during hospital stay on postnatal unit.	
	Question	Answer (Y/N)	Notes
Temporality	Hypothesised direction	Yes	Pregnancy complications occur during pregnancy before stay on postnatal unit
	Reverse direction	No	
Face-validity	Hypothesised direction	Yes	It seems plausible that mothers with pregnancy complications require more care during postnatal period, thus influencing staffing exposure
	Reverse direction	No	
Recourse to theory	Hypothesised direction	Yes	Women with diabetes need augmented blood sugar monitoring and nursing interventions after birth due to higher

			<p>risk of hypoglycaemia which has influence on staffing exposure. (5)</p> <p>Women who have experienced eclampsia require augmented care on intensive care unit before being transferred to the postnatal ward. After transfer on postnatal unit, they require close monitoring and enhanced nursing interventions to ensure their safety which has influence on staffing exposure. (6)</p>
	Reverse direction	No	
Counterfactual	Counterfactual exposure	Presence vs. absence of pregnancy complication	
	Counterfactual question	How would pregnancy complications affect the proportion of target nurse-to-patient ratio during the hospital stay on the postnatal unit?	
	Hypothesised outcome	We expect there would be a higher nurse-to-patient ratio.	
	Further justification or suggested mechanism	Mothers with pregnancy complications require increased monitoring, nursing	

			interventions and support for recovery after birth	
		Reverse counterfactual exposure	NA	
		Reverse counterfactual question	NA	
		Reverse hypothesized outcome	NA	
		Further justification or suggested mechanism	NA	
	Conclusion	Retain		

Edge ID (3)		Variable From	Variable To	Assessed Prior
	Variable	Pregnancy complications	Risk of hypoglycaemia	Yes – IG DAG Breastfeeding
	Measurement	ICD Diagnoses, if at least one is present, it is a yes	Feeding intervention to prevent hypoglycaemia	
		Question	Answer (Y/N)	Notes
	Temporality	Hypothesised direction	Yes	Pregnancy complications happen during or after labour and before feeding intervention
		Reverse direction	No	Feeding intervention cannot influence past pregnancy complications
	Face-validity	Hypothesised direction	Yes	It seems plausible that pregnancy complications like diabetes can lead to complications for the newborn which has influence on its glucose metabolism
		Reverse direction	No	
	Recourse to theory	Hypothesised direction	Yes	Infants of diabetic mothers are at higher risk of hypoglycaemia (7,9)

			Maternal hypertension (OR 3.07, 95% CI 1.51–6.30, p = 0.002) was the sole risk factor for neonatal hypoglycaemia (10)
		Reverse direction	No
Counterfactual	Counterfactual exposure	Pregnancy complications vs. absence of pregnancy complications	Of the 134 infants of diabetic mothers whose early feeding was breast feeding, hypoglycaemia affected 30% which was corrected with oral feedings in 78% of the cases (8)
	Counterfactual question	How would the presence of pregnancy complications affect the likelihood of neonatal hypoglycaemia?	
	Hypothesised outcome	We expect there would be a higher rate of neonatal hypoglycaemia.	
	Further justification or suggested mechanism	Maternal diabetes leads to high fetal glucose levels with compensatory hyperinsulinemia. After separation from mother, the hyperinsulinemia in the newborns' metabolism causes neonatal hypoglycaemia	

	Reverse counterfactual exposure	NA	
	Reverse counterfactual question	NA	
	Reverse hypothesized outcome	NA	
	Further justification or suggested mechanism	NA	
Conclusion	Retain		

Edge ID (4)	Variable From	Variable To	Assessed Prior
Variable	Labour complications	Staffing exposure (postnatal unit)	Yes – IG DAG Breastfeeding
Measurement	ICD Diagnosis and CHOP codes to identify the complications. Dichotomised, yes/no, if at least one of the conditions is present.	Proportion of target nurse-to-patient ratio during hospital stay on postnatal unit.	
	Question	Answer (Y/N)	Notes
Temporality	Hypothesised direction	Yes	Labour complications occur during birth before stay on postnatal unit with its staffing exposure
	Reverse direction	No	Staffing on postnatal unit cannot influence passed labour
Face-validity	Hypothesised direction	Yes	It is plausible that a mother with labour complications requires more monitoring and nursing interventions during postnatal stay, thus labour complications have an influence on staffing
	Reverse direction	No	
Recourse to theory	Hypothesised direction	Yes	High-grade perineal tear requires postnatal surgery which necessitates increased nursing interventions.

			(11) A postpartum haemorrhage requires more staffing on postnatal unit for augmented monitoring, pain management and emotional support as a postpartum haemorrhage can be traumatising for the mother (risk for posttraumatic stress syndrome). (12,45)
	Reverse direction	No	
Counterfactual	Counterfactual exposure	Presence vs. absence of labour complications	
	Counterfactual question	How would presence of labour complications affect proportion of target nurse-to-patient ratio during hospital stay on postnatal unit?	
	Hypothesised outcome	We expect that the presence of labour complications would necessitate a higher proportion of nurse-to-patient ratio to provide adequate care.	
	Further justification or suggested mechanism	Women with labour complications require more monitoring and nursing interventions to ensure patient safety	
	Reverse counterfactual exposure	NA	
	Reverse counterfactual question	NA	

		Reverse hypothesized outcome	NA	
		Further justification or suggested mechanism	NA	
	Conclusion	Retain		

Edge ID (5)		Variable From	Variable To	Assessed Prior
	Variable	Labour complications	Risk of hypoglycaemia	No
	Measurement	ICD Diagnosis and CHOP codes to identify the complications. Dichotomised, yes/no, if at least one of the conditions is present.	Feeding intervention to prevent hypoglycaemia	
		Question	Answer (Y/N)	Notes
	Temporality	Hypothesised direction	Yes	Labour complications occur during delivery before feeding intervention to prevent hypoglycaemia
		Reverse direction	No	Feeding intervention to prevent hypoglycaemia cannot influence past delivery with possible labour complications
	Face-validity	Hypothesised direction	Yes	It seems plausible that long length of labour can stress the newborn physically which may have an influence on their glucose metabolism
		Reverse direction	No	
	Recourse to theory	Hypothesised direction	Yes	Mothers of neonates with hypoglycaemia had more blood loss (13) Maternal and fetal stress are risk

			factors for neonatal hypoglycaemia (14)22.10.2024 16:26:00
	Reverse direction	No	
Counterfactual	Counterfactual exposure	Presence vs. absence of labour complications	
	Counterfactual question	How does the presence of labour complications affect the risk of hypoglycaemia?	
	Hypothesised outcome	We expect that the presence of labour complications would increase the risk of hypoglycaemia	
	Further justification or suggested mechanism	Labour complications increase the newborns' physiological stress which requires more glucose from their metabolism and increases their risk of hypoglycaemia	
	Reverse counterfactual exposure	NA	
	Reverse counterfactual question	NA	
	Reverse hypothesized outcome	NA	
	Further justification or suggested mechanism	NA	
Conclusion	Retain		

Edge ID (6)	Variable From	Variable To	Assessed Prior
Variable	Labour complications	Risk of hypothermia	No
Measurement	ICD Diagnosis and CHOP codes to identify the complications. Dichotomised, yes/no,	No measurement available	

		if at least one of the conditions is present.	
	Question	Answer (Y/N)	Notes
Temporality	Hypothesised direction	Yes	Labour complications occur during or shortly after delivery and may have an influence on the newborn's body temperature
	Reverse direction	No	
Face-validity	Hypothesised direction	Yes	It seems plausible that labour complications like long length of labour can stress the newborn physically which may cause cold stress due to increased glucose metabolism
	Reverse direction	No	
Recourse to theory	Hypothesised direction	Yes	Rate of birth asphyxia-related complications (hypothermia included) gradually increased with duration of second stage labour: from 0.42% at < 1 h to 1.29% at ≥ 4 h (adjusted RR 2.46 (95% CI 1.66 to 3.66)) (15)
	Reverse direction	No	
Counterfactual	Counterfactual exposure	Presence vs. absence of labour complications	
	Counterfactual question	How does the presence of labour complications affect the risk of hypothermia?	
	Hypothesised outcome	We expect that the presence of labour complications	

			would increase the risk of hypothermia	
	Further justification or suggested mechanism		Labour complications increase the newborns' physiological stress which requires more glucose from their metabolism and increases their risk of hypoglycaemia which on the other hand increases the risk of hypothermia	
	Reverse counterfactual exposure		NA	
	Reverse counterfactual question		NA	
	Reverse hypothesized outcome		NA	
	Further justification or suggested mechanism		NA	
Conclusion	Delete			Path is mediated by risk of hypoglycaemia. Therefore direct edge to be deleted.

Edge ID (7)	Variable From	Variable To	Assessed Prior
Variable	Gestational age	Staffing exposure (postnatal unit)	Yes – IG DAG Breastfeeding
Measurement	Duration of pregnancy in days (from BFS data)	Proportion of target nurse-to-patient ratio during hospital stay on postnatal unit.	
	Question	Answer (Y/N)	Notes
Temporality	Hypothesised direction	Yes	Gestational age should logically stand before nurse-to-patient ratios on postnatal unit
	Reverse direction	No	It is not plausible that the proportion

			of nurse-to-patient ratios would influence the gestational age of the pregnancy.
Face-validity	Hypothesised direction	Yes	Gestational age could influence nurse-to-patient ratios. Newborns with lower gestational ages might require more staffing.
	Reverse direction	No	
Recourse to theory	Hypothesised direction	Yes	Late preterm infants are at high risk for medical complications such as respiratory issues, hyperbilirubinemia, poor feeding, temperature instability and infections. Frequent assessments are needed, influencing staffing exposure. In some hospitals, late preterm infants' cribs are marked as a reminder of the need for extended assessments. (16)
	Reverse direction	No	
Counterfactual	Counterfactual exposure	All women have gestational age of 36 weeks or less	
	Counterfactual question	Would there be a different nurse-to-patient ratio during hospital stay on postnatal unit if the gestational age of all women in labour was 36 or less weeks?	
	Hypothesised outcome	A higher nurse-to-patient ratio during	

			hospital stay on postnatal unit may be required to address specific risks associated with late preterm gestations.	
		Further justification or suggested mechanism	Lower gestational ages may present complications requiring increased care to manage potential risks.	
		Reverse counterfactual exposure	NA	
		Reverse counterfactual question	NA	
		Reverse hypothesized outcome	NA	
		Further justification or suggested mechanism	NA	
	Conclusion	Retain		

Edge ID (8)		Variable From	Variable To	Assessed Prior
	Variable	Gestational age	Birth weight	Yes – IG DAG Breastfeeding/ IG DAG Birth
	Measurement	Duration of pregnancy in days (from BFS data)	Weight in kg measured directly after birth	
		Question	Answer (Y/N)	Notes
	Temporality	Hypothesised direction	Yes	Gestational age influences development and therefore weight of fetus
		Reverse direction	No	Birth weight of baby is measured after birth when pregnancy and therefore gestational age is over. It cannot influence gestational age.
	Face-validity	Hypothesised direction	Yes	It seems plausible that higher

			gestational ages result in higher birth weight due to longer period of fetal growth
	Reverse direction	No	
Recourse to theory	Hypothesised direction	Yes	They observed a clear increase in birthweight by gestational age for all term weeks. (17)
	Reverse direction	No	
Counterfactual	Counterfactual exposure	Different gestational ages, e.g. 36+0 weeks vs. 40+0 weeks	
	Counterfactual question	How would different gestational ages affect birth weight?	
	Hypothesised outcome	We expect there would be a higher birth weight in term newborns (40+0 weeks) than in late preterm newborns (36+0 weeks)	
	Further justification or suggested mechanism	NA	
	Reverse counterfactual exposure	NA	
	Reverse counterfactual question	NA	
	Reverse hypothesized outcome	NA	
	Further justification or suggested mechanism	NA	
Conclusion	Retain		

Edge ID (9)	Variable From	Variable To	Assessed Prior
Variable	Gestational age	Risk of hyperbilirubinaemia	No
Measurement	Duration of pregnancy in days (from BFS data)	No measurement available	
	Question	Answer (Y/N)	Notes

	Temporality	Hypothesised direction	Yes	Gestational age is determined before birth and can influence the risk of hyperbilirubinaemia
		Reverse direction	No	
	Face-validity	Hypothesised direction	Yes	It is plausible that low gestational age is associated with hyperbilirubinaemia due to immature liver function
		Reverse direction	No	
	Recourse to theory	Hypothesised direction	Yes	Newborns of gestational age 37-38 weeks were more likely to be diagnosed with neonatal jaundice (aOR 2.83, 95% CI [2.75-2.92]) than newborns of gestational age >41 weeks (aOR 0.63, 95% CI [0.59-0.67]) (18) Newborns of low gestational age were at increased risk of developing severe hyperbilirubinaemia (OR, 1.71; 95% CI [1.40-2.11]) (24)
		Reverse direction	No	
	Counterfactual	Counterfactual exposure	Different gestational ages, e.g. 36+0 weeks vs. 40+0 weeks	
		Counterfactual question	How would different gestational ages affect the risk of hyperbilirubinaemia?	
		Hypothesised outcome	We expect there would be a higher rate of hyperbilirubinaemia	

			in late preterms (36+0 weeks).	
	Further justification or suggested mechanism		Late preterms have higher bilirubin levels and immature liver function which increases the risk of hyperbilirubinaemia	
	Reverse counterfactual exposure		NA	
	Reverse counterfactual question		NA	
	Reverse hypothesized outcome		NA	
	Further justification or suggested mechanism		NA	
	Conclusion	Retain		

Edge ID (10)	Variable From	Variable To	Assessed Prior
Variable	Gestational age	Risk of hypothermia	No
Measurement	Duration of pregnancy in days (from BFS data)	No measurement available	
	Question	Answer (Y/N)	Notes
Temporality	Hypothesised direction	Yes	Gestational age is determined before birth and can influence the risk of hypothermia
	Reverse direction	No	
Face-validity	Hypothesised direction	Yes	It is plausible that low gestational age newborns are at higher risk of hypothermia
	Reverse direction	No	
Recourse to theory	Hypothesised direction	Yes	Premature newborns are at higher risk of hypothermia (OR 2.51, 95% CI [1.77–3.55], p<0.001) (20) Newborns of gestational age 35

			were at higher risk of moderate/severe hypothermia (OR 3.17, 95% CI [2.24–4.49] (19))
	Reverse direction	No	
Counterfactual	Counterfactual exposure	Different gestational ages, e.g. 36+0 weeks vs. 40+0 weeks	
	Counterfactual question	How would different gestational ages affect the risk of hypothermia?	
	Hypothesised outcome	We expect there would be a higher rate of hypothermia in late preterms (36+0 weeks).	
	Further justification or suggested mechanism	Preterm newborns have a larger body surface in relation of their weight, thinner skin, insufficient fat tissue and immature thermoregulation mechanisms which increase the risk of hypothermia	
	Reverse counterfactual exposure	NA	
	Reverse counterfactual question	NA	
	Reverse hypothesized outcome	NA	
	Further justification or suggested mechanism	NA	
Conclusion	Retain		

Edge ID (11)	Variable	Variable From	Variable To	Assessed Prior
		Birth weight	Staffing exposure (postnatal unit)	Yes – IG DAG Breastfeeding

	Measurement	Weight in kg measured directly after birth	Proportion of target nurse-to-patient ratio during hospital stay on postnatal unit.	
		Question	Answer (Y/N)	Notes
	Temporality	Hypothesised direction	Yes	Birth weight is measured directly after birth before staffing exposure on postnatal unit
		Reverse direction	No	
	Face-validity	Hypothesised direction	Yes	Low birth weight is associated with a higher risk of complications and requires more monitoring which could influence staffing exposure on postnatal unit
		Reverse direction	No	
	Recourse to theory	Hypothesised direction	Yes	Newborns with low and high birth weight require additional monitoring (glucose management, vital signs), feeding assistance and further interventions (temperature management) (21) which necessitates a higher nurse-to-patient ratio
		Reverse direction	No	
	Counterfactual	Counterfactual exposure	Low vs. high birth weight	
		Counterfactual question	How would different birth weights affect staffing exposure on postnatal unit?	
		Hypothesised outcome	We expect that newborns with low and high birth weights would require higher staffing ratios due	

			to increased medical and care needs.	
	Further justification or suggested mechanism		Newborns with low and high birth weight are more likely to suffer from complications and require additional monitoring, feeding support and further medical interventions.	
	Reverse counterfactual exposure		NA	
	Reverse counterfactual question		NA	
	Reverse hypothesized outcome		NA	
	Further justification or suggested mechanism		NA	
	Conclusion	Retain		

Edge ID (12)	Variable From	Variable To	Assessed Prior
Variable	Birth weight	Risk of hypoglycaemia	Yes – IG DAG Breastfeeding
Measurement	Weight in kg measured directly after birth	Feeding intervention to prevent hypoglycaemia	
	Question	Answer (Y/N)	Notes
Temporality	Hypothesised direction	Yes	Birth weight precedes the risk of hypoglycaemia
	Reverse direction	No	
Face-validity	Hypothesised direction	Yes	It is plausible that birth weight affects the metabolism
	Reverse direction	No	Risk of hypoglycaemia does not affect birth weight
Recourse to theory	Hypothesised direction	Yes	Of 152 small newborns ($\leq 10^{\text{th}}$ percentile or

			<p>≤2500g), 77 had hypoglycaemia (52%), of 133 large newborns, 61 had hypoglycaemia (47%) (9)</p> <p>The risk of neonatal hypoglycaemia increased significantly as the birth weight percentile increased (22,23)10/22/2024 4:26:00 PM</p>
	Reverse direction	No	
Counterfactual	Counterfactual exposure	Normal vs. high birth weight	
	Counterfactual question	Would the risk of hypoglycaemia differ in normal vs. high birth weight?	
	Hypothesised outcome	We expect that newborns with high birth weight had an increased risk of hypoglycaemia	
	Further justification or suggested mechanism	Newborns with high birth weight have an increased risk for hyperinsulinemia (often due to maternal diabetes)	
	Reverse counterfactual exposure	NA	
	Reverse counterfactual question	NA	
	Reverse hypothesized outcome	NA	
	Further justification or suggested mechanism	NA	
Conclusion	Retain		

Edge ID (13)	Variable From	Variable To	Assessed Prior
Variable	Birth weight	Risk of hypothermia	No
Measurement	Weight in kg measured directly after birth	No measurement available	
	Question	Answer (Y/N)	Notes
Temporality	Hypothesised direction	Yes	Birth weight stands before risk of hypothermia
	Reverse direction	No	
Face-validity	Hypothesised direction	Yes	It is plausible that newborns of low birthweight are at higher risk of hypothermia due to less bodyfat and larger body surface in relation of their weight
	Reverse direction	No	
Recourse to theory	Hypothesised direction	Yes	Newborns of low birth weight are at higher risk of neonatal hypothermia: OR 1.73, 95% CI [1.45 – 2.07] (20,21) Newborns ≤2500g were at higher risk of moderate/severe hypothermia: OR 5.97, 95% CI [4.45– 8.00] (19)
	Reverse direction	No	
Counterfactual	Counterfactual exposure	Low vs. high birth weight	
	Counterfactual question	How would different birth weights affect the risk of hypothermia?	
	Hypothesised outcome	We expect newborns with low birth weight to be at higher risk of hypothermia.	

	Further justification or suggested mechanism	Newborns of low birth weight have less insulating body fat and a larger body surface in relation of their weight, which increases heat loss and the risk of hypothermia	
	Reverse counterfactual exposure	NA	
	Reverse counterfactual question	NA	
	Reverse hypothesized outcome	NA	
	Further justification or suggested mechanism	NA	
Conclusion	Retain		

Edge ID (14)	Variable From	Variable To	Assessed Prior
Variable	Birth weight	Risk of hyperbilirubinaemia	No
Measurement	Weight in kg measured directly after birth	Measured bilirubin values, temperatures, glucose values from surveillance curve + Movement data for transfer	
	Question	Answer (Y/N)	Notes
Temporality	Hypothesised direction	Yes	Birth weight precedes risk of hyperbilirubinaemia
	Reverse direction	No	
Face-validity	Hypothesised direction	Yes	It is plausible that birth weight has an influence on risk of hyperbilirubinaemia as low birth weight might be associated with lack of nutrition during pregnancy which might interfere with liver function
	Reverse direction	No	

	Recourse to theory	Hypothesised direction	Yes	Underweight newborns were at increased risk of severe hyperbilirubinaemia (OR, 6.26; 95% CI, 1.23–31.86, p = 0.027, I ² = 99.1%) (24)
		Reverse direction	No	
	Counterfactual	Counterfactual exposure	Low vs. high birth weight	
		Counterfactual question	How would different birth weights affect the risk of hyperbilirubinaemia?	
		Hypothesised outcome	We expect there would be a higher rate of hyperbilirubinaemia in newborns with low birth weight.	
		Further justification or suggested mechanism	Newborns with low birth weight may have immature liver function which increases the risk of hyperbilirubinaemia	
		Reverse counterfactual exposure	NA	
		Reverse counterfactual question	NA	
		Reverse hypothesized outcome	NA	
		Further justification or suggested mechanism	NA	
	Conclusion	Retain		

Edge ID (15)	Variable	Variable From	Variable To	Assessed Prior
	Variable	Maternal age	Staffing exposure (postnatal unit)	Yes – IG DAG Breastfeeding
	Measurement	Age in years	Proportion of target nurse-to-patient ratio during hospital stay on postnatal unit.	

	Question	Answer (Y/N)	Notes
Temporality	Hypothesised direction	Yes	Maternal age stands before staffing exposure (postnatal unit)
	Reverse direction	No	
Face-validity	Hypothesised direction	Yes	Older women might be more experienced with health care system and be more likely to request care than younger women
	Reverse direction	No	Staffing exposure (postnatal unit) does not influence maternal age
Recourse to theory	Hypothesised direction	Yes	Women >35 years were more satisfied with care on postnatal ward than women aged 16-24 years (25). This could be because older mothers are more likely to know what they want and feel confident in asking for help, whereas younger mothers may have less experience and confidence in clearly expressing their needs.
	Reverse direction	No	
Counterfactual	Counterfactual exposure	Different maternal ages	
	Counterfactual question	How would different maternal ages affect the proportion of target nurse-to-patient ratio during the hospital stay on the postnatal unit?	
	Hypothesised outcome	We expect that certain age groups require higher or lower nurse-to-	

			patient ratios due to varying levels of care needs.	
	Further justification or suggested mechanism		Younger mothers might need more educational and emotional support while older mothers might have more medical complications requiring closer monitoring.	
	Reverse counterfactual exposure	NA		
	Reverse counterfactual question	NA		
	Reverse hypothesized outcome	NA		
	Further justification or suggested mechanism	NA		
	Conclusion	Retain		

Edge ID (16)	Variable From	Variable To	Assessed Prior
Variable	Maternal age	Risk of hypothermia	No
Measurement	Age in years	No measurement available	
	Question	Answer (Y/N)	Notes
Temporality	Hypothesised direction	Yes	Maternal age is determined before birth of newborn and its risk of hypothermia
	Reverse direction	No	
Face-validity	Hypothesised direction	Yes	It seems plausible that women of different ages have different levels of experience, confidence and support which may have an impact on the newborn's risk of hypothermia
	Reverse direction	No	

	Recourse to theory	Hypothesised direction	Yes	Newborns of adolescent mothers (<19 years) had a higher incidence of hypothermia compared to newborns of mothers >20 years (p=0.025). (26) Maternal age showed an association with moderate/severe hypothermia in a retrospective cohort study with 23,549 infants (OR, 1.12; 95% CI, 1.05–1.20) (19)
		Reverse direction	No	
	Counterfactual	Counterfactual exposure	Different maternal ages, e.g. <20 years, >30 years	
		Counterfactual question	How would different maternal ages affect the risk of hypothermia in newborns?	
		Hypothesised outcome	We expect newborns of mothers <20 years to be at higher risk of hypothermia.	
		Further justification or suggested mechanism	Younger women may have less experience, confidence and support which may have an impact on the newborn's risk of hypothermia	
		Reverse counterfactual exposure	NA	
		Reverse counterfactual question	NA	
		Reverse hypothesized outcome	NA	

	Further justification or suggested mechanism	NA	
Conclusion	Retain		

Edge ID (17)	Variable From	Variable To	Assessed Prior
Variable	Parity	Staffing exposure (postnatal unit)	Yes – IG DAG Breastfeeding
Measurement	Parity, number of children born before (from BFS data).	Proportion of target nurse-to-patient ratio during hospital stay on postnatal unit.	
	Question	Answer (Y/N)	Notes
Temporality	Hypothesised direction	Yes	Parity exists before stay on postnatal unit and its staffing exposure
	Reverse direction	No	
Face-validity	Hypothesised direction	Yes	It is plausible that multiparous women are more experienced with postnatal care and may need less support than nulliparous women
	Reverse direction	No	
Recourse to theory	Hypothesised direction	Yes	Primiparous women required more postnatal support from midwives than multiparous women. (27) Multiparity is associated with lower risk of adverse birth outcomes (28) which may require less need of postnatal care. Nulliparous women are at higher risk of emergency caesarean than

			<p>multiparous women (29), which may require more frequent postnatal care.</p>
	Reverse direction	No	
Counterfactual	Counterfactual exposure	Primiparity vs. multiparity	
	Counterfactual question	How would different statuses of parity affect staffing exposure on postnatal ward?	
	Hypothesised outcome	We expect that primiparous women need more care and support than multiparous women	
	Further justification or suggested mechanism	Primiparous women are at higher risk for labour complications and may need more care and support after birth which influences staffing exposure	
	Reverse counterfactual exposure	NA	
	Reverse counterfactual question	NA	
	Reverse hypothesized outcome	NA	
	Further justification or suggested mechanism	NA	
Conclusion	Retain		

Edge ID (18)	Variable From	Variable To	Assessed Prior
Variable	Parity	Risk of hypothermia	No
Measurement	Parity, number of children born before (from BFS data).	No measurement available	
	Question	Answer (Y/N)	Notes

	Temporality	Hypothesised direction	Yes	Parity is determined before birth of newborn and its risk of hypothermia
		Reverse direction	No	
	Face-validity	Hypothesised direction	Yes	Nulliparous women might be less experienced and self-confident in care of newborn, potentially increasing its risk of hypothermia
		Reverse direction	No	
	Recourse to theory	Hypothesised direction	No	Nulliparity is not associated with hypothermia (OR 0.71, 95% CI [0.39 – 1.29], p=0.26), primiparity neither (OR 0.69, 95% CI [0.38 – 1.27], p=0.23) (30)
		Reverse direction	No	
	Counterfactual	Counterfactual exposure	NA	
		Counterfactual question	NA	
		Hypothesised outcome	NA	
		Further justification or suggested mechanism	NA	
		Reverse counterfactual exposure	NA	
		Reverse counterfactual question	NA	
		Reverse hypothesized outcome	NA	
		Further justification or suggested mechanism	NA	
Conclusion	Delete			

Edge ID (19)	Variable	Variable From	Variable To	Assessed Prior
		Mode of birth	Staffing exposure (postnatal unit)	Yes – IG DAG Breastfeeding

Measurement	ICD Diagnoses and CHOP codes to define mode of birth.	Proportion of target nurse-to-patient ratio during hospital stay on postnatal unit.	
	Question	Answer (Y/N)	Notes
Temporality	Hypothesised direction	Yes	Birth precedes stay on postnatal ward
	Reverse direction	No	Staffing on postnatal ward cannot influence past mode of birth
Face-validity	Hypothesised direction	Yes	It is plausible that different modes of birth have influence on staffing exposure on postnatal ward due to different needs of care and support
	Reverse direction	No	
Recourse to theory	Hypothesised direction	Yes	For woman after caesarean, intensive medical care is more often required than after a vaginal birth. (31)
	Reverse direction	No	
Counterfactual	Counterfactual exposure	Different modes of birth (e.g. vaginal birth vs. caesarean)	
	Counterfactual question	How would different modes of birth affect the staffing exposure on the postnatal unit?	
	Hypothesised outcome	We expect that woman after caesarean require higher staffing ratios due to increased medical needs.	
	Further justification or suggested mechanism	Women after caesarean need more intensive	

			monitoring due to potential complications like thrombosis	
	Reverse counterfactual exposure	NA		
	Reverse counterfactual question	NA		
	Reverse hypothesized outcome	NA		
	Further justification or suggested mechanism	NA		
	Conclusion	Retain		

Edge ID (20)	Variable From	Variable To	Assessed Prior
Variable	Mode of birth	Risk of hypoglycaemia	Yes – IG DAG Breastfeeding
Measurement	ICD Diagnoses and CHOP codes to define mode of birth.	Feeding intervention to prevent hypoglycaemia	
	Question	Answer (Y/N)	Notes
Temporality	Hypothesised direction	Yes	Mode of birth precedes feeding intervention due to risk of hypoglycaemia
	Reverse direction	No	
Face-validity	Hypothesised direction	Yes	It seems plausible that mode of delivery has an influence on risk of hypoglycaemia due to different timing of first breastfeed or differences in stress during labour
	Reverse direction	No	
Recourse to theory	Hypothesised direction		Caesarean section (OR 2.38, 95% CI 1.56 – 3.65) was associated with an increased risk for neonatal hypoglycaemia (7)

		Reverse direction		
	Counterfactual	Counterfactual exposure	Different modes of birth (e.g., vaginal birth vs. caesarean section)	
		Counterfactual question	How would different modes of birth affect the risk of hypoglycaemia?	
		Hypothesised outcome	We expect that caesareans might be associated with higher rates of hypoglycaemia.	
		Further justification or suggested mechanism	Vaginal births mostly allow immediate skin to skin contact and early initiation of breastfeeding while caesareans might lead to separation from mother and child which delays initiation of breastfeeding which increases risk of hypoglycaemia	
		Reverse counterfactual exposure	NA	
		Reverse counterfactual question	NA	
		Reverse hypothesized outcome	NA	
		Further justification or suggested mechanism	NA	
	Conclusion	Retain		

Edge ID (21)	Variable	Variable From	Variable To	Assessed Prior
	Variable	Mode of birth	Risk of hyperbilirubinaemia	No
	Measurement	ICD Diagnoses and CHOP codes to define mode of birth.	Measured bilirubin values, temperatures, glucose values from surveillance	

	Question	Answer (Y/N)	Notes
Temporality	Hypothesised direction	Yes	Mode of birth precedes risk of hyperbilirubinaemia
	Reverse direction	No	The risk of hyperbilirubinaemia does not affect mode of birth
Face-validity	Hypothesised direction	Yes	It seems plausible that mode of birth with risk of bruising can have an influence on hyperbilirubinaemia
	Reverse direction	No	
Recourse to theory	Hypothesised direction	Yes	Newborns after vacuum extraction are more likely to develop hyperbilirubinaemia (aOR 2.22, 95% CI [2.15 – 2.31]) than newborns after planned caesarean (aOR 0.45, 95% CI [0.42 – 0.48]) (18)
	Reverse direction	No	
Counterfactual	Counterfactual exposure	Different modes of birth	
	Counterfactual question	How would different modes of birth affect the risk of hyperbilirubinaemia in newborns?	
	Hypothesised outcome	We expect there would be a higher rate of newborns with hyperbilirubinaemia if all births were vacuum extracted.	
	Further justification or suggested mechanism	Due to increased degradation of haemoglobin from	

			extra vasal blood (cephalhematoma)	
	Reverse counterfactual exposure	NA		
	Reverse counterfactual question	NA		
	Reverse hypothesized outcome	NA		
	Further justification or suggested mechanism	NA		
	Conclusion	Retain		

Edge ID (22)		Variable From	Variable To	Assessed Prior
	Variable	Country of birth/ethnicity	Staffing exposure (postnatal unit)	Yes – IG DAG Breastfeeding
	Measurement	Citizenship & language	Proportion of target nurse-to-patient ratio during hospital stay on postnatal unit.	
		Question	Answer (Y/N)	Notes
	Temporality	Hypothesised direction	Yes	Birth of woman happens before Staffing exposure (postnatal unit)
		Reverse direction	No	
	Face-validity	Hypothesised direction	Yes	Immigrants may have less knowledge about health care system and might request less care due to language barriers.
		Reverse direction	No	
	Recourse to theory	Hypothesised direction	Yes	Immigrant women are more often unaware of postpartum services, so they are unlikely to ask for support which has influence on staffing exposure (33)

			Immigrant women experienced difficulties with nurses, including communication barriers, lack of empathy, perceived bias due to accents, and feeling disrespected or not taken seriously (32) Thus, they might refrain from seeking support from nurses on postpartum unit.
	Reverse direction	No	
Counterfactual	Counterfactual exposure	Different country of birth/ethnicity (immigrants vs. native-born women)	
	Counterfactual question	How would demand on staffing on postnatal unit differ if the mother's country of birth/ethnicity were different?	
	Hypothesised outcome	We expect that there would be a higher staffing demand if all mothers on postnatal ward were of foreign origin.	
	Further justification or suggested mechanism	Intercultural communicative barriers might require special trained staff	
	Reverse counterfactual exposure	NA	
	Reverse counterfactual question	NA	
	Reverse hypothesized outcome	NA	
	Further justification or suggested mechanism	NA	

	Conclusion	Retain		
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Edge ID (23)		Variable From	Variable To	Assessed Prior
	Variable	Country of birth/ethnicity	Risk of hypothermia	No
	Measurement	Citizenship & language	No measurement available	
		Question	Answer (Y/N)	Notes
	Temporality	Hypothesised direction	Yes	Citizenship of mother stands before birth and risk of hypothermia
		Reverse direction	No	
	Face-validity	Hypothesised direction		It is plausible that the citizenship of mother with its cultural, social and economic influences affects practices of newborn care and might have an influence on the risk of hypothermia
		Reverse direction	No	The risk of hypothermia does not affect mother's citizenship
	Recourse to theory	Hypothesised direction	Yes	Newborns of Asian (aOR, 1.94; 95% CI [1.61–2.34]) and Black race mothers (aOR, 2.65; 95% CI [1.78–3.96]) had the highest adjusted odds of hypothermia (19)
		Reverse direction	No	
	Counterfactual	Counterfactual exposure	Different ethnicities of mother	
		Counterfactual question	How would different ethnicities of mother affect the risk of hypothermia?	

	Hypothesised outcome	We expect that newborns of mothers of certain ethnicities would be more likely to develop hypothermia	
	Further justification or suggested mechanism	NA	
	Reverse counterfactual exposure	NA	
	Reverse counterfactual question	NA	
	Reverse hypothesized outcome	NA	
	Further justification or suggested mechanism	NA	
	Conclusion	Retain	

Edge ID (24)	Variable From	Variable To	Assessed Prior
Variable	Risk of hypoglycaemia	Staffing exposure (postnatal unit)	Yes – IG DAG Breastfeeding
Measurement	Feeding intervention to prevent hypoglycaemia	Proportion of target nurse-to-patient ratio during hospital stay on postnatal unit.	
	Question	Answer (Y/N)	Notes
Temporality	Hypothesised direction	Yes	Risk of hypoglycaemia precedes nurse-to-patient ratio
	Reverse direction	No	
Face-validity	Hypothesised direction	Yes	It is plausible that newborns with risk of hypoglycaemia need more monitoring which requires a higher nurse-to-patient ratio
	Reverse direction	No	
Recourse to theory	Hypothesised direction	Yes	All newborns were breast or formula fed in the first hour after birth. Plasma

			<p>glucoses were measured 30min thereafter. If glucose was <25mg/L, feeding had to be repeated immediately and glucose was rechecked 1h later. If glucose value stayed <25mg/dL, i.v. glucose was started. Plasma glucose monitoring was performed every 2-3 hours. This protocol presents the increased workload for staffing due to frequent interventions and monitoring. (35)</p> <p>The authors advocate accepting some degree of overtreatment to prevent long-term impairment from hypoglycaemia (34)</p>
	Reverse direction	No	<p>Influence of midwife staffing on risk of hypoglycaemia in newborns not yet scrutinized (4)</p> <p>Nurses were worried about bad outcomes for the baby due to less frequent assessments in the context of being too busy (1)</p>

	Counterfactual	Counterfactual exposure	Feeding interventions vs. no feeding intervention to prevent hypoglycaemia	
		Counterfactual question	How would the feeding intervention to prevent hypoglycaemia affect nurse-to-patient ratio during hospital stay on postnatal unit?	
		Hypothesised outcome	We expect there would be a higher nurse-to-patient ratio during hospital stay on postnatal unit if there were numerous feeding interventions to prevent hypoglycaemia.	
		Further justification or suggested mechanism	Newborns with risk for hypoglycaemia need rigorous monitoring and feeding interventions to prevent hypoglycaemia	
		Reverse counterfactual exposure	NA	
		Reverse counterfactual question	NA	
		Reverse hypothesized outcome	NA	
		Further justification or suggested mechanism	NA	
	Conclusion		Retain	

Edge ID (25)		Variable From	Variable To	Assessed Prior
	Variable	Risk of hypothermia	Risk of hypoglycaemia	No
	Measurement	No measurement available	Feeding intervention to prevent hypoglycaemia	

	Question	Answer (Y/N)	Notes
Temporality	Hypothesised direction	Yes	Risk of hypothermia could precede hypoglycaemia
	Reverse direction	Yes	Risk of hypoglycaemia could precede risk of hypothermia
Face-validity	Hypothesised direction	Yes	(Risk of) hypothermia could impair glucose production and increase risk of hypoglycaemia
	Reverse direction	Yes	It is plausible that risk of hypoglycaemia can increase the risk of hypothermia due to low blood glucose levels
Recourse to theory	Hypothesised direction	Yes	<p>It is difficult to prove if hypothermia is a cause or an effect of hypoglycaemia. (38)</p> <p>The authors of the guideline about neonatal resuscitation found seven studies (very-low-quality, downgraded for risk of bias and indirectness) showing a significant association between hypothermia (<36°C) and hypoglycaemia. Two of these studies, using</p>

			historical controls, showed improved glycaemic control with improved normothermia. (37)
			A comprehensive review of guidelines of neonatal hypoglycaemia reveals general agreement in the avoidance of cold stress and hypothermia. (36)
	Reverse direction	No	
Counterfactual	Counterfactual exposure	Risk of hypothermia vs. no risk of hypothermia	
	Counterfactual question	How would the risk of hypothermia affect the risk of hypoglycaemia?	
	Hypothesised outcome	We expect there would be a higher risk of hypoglycaemia	
	Further justification or suggested mechanism	Newborns at risk of hypothermia may have a higher need for glucose to maintain body temperature and are more likely to be preterm with immature metabolic functions	
	Reverse counterfactual exposure	NA	
	Reverse counterfactual question	NA	
	Reverse hypothesized outcome	NA	
	Further justification or suggested mechanism	NA	
Conclusion	Retain		

Edge ID (26)	Variable	Variable From	Variable To	Assessed Prior
		Feeding method (Breastfeeding/Bottle)	Risk of hypoglycaemia	No

Measurement	Feeding entries from EHR to define breastfeeding, bottle feeding or mixed.	Feeding intervention to prevent hypoglycaemia	
	Question	Answer (Y/N)	Notes
Temporality	Hypothesised direction	No	Feeding method does not precede risk of hypoglycaemia (except via mediator hypothermia)
	Reverse direction	Yes	Risk of hypoglycaemia may precede feeding method
Face-validity	Hypothesised direction	No	
	Reverse direction	Yes	It is plausible that risk of hypoglycaemia has an influence on feeding method as preventive intervention
Recourse to theory	Hypothesised direction	No	
	Reverse direction	Yes	The Swiss neonatal society recommends that newborns at risk of hypoglycaemia should be breastfed instantly after birth. After breastfeeding session, formula milk (5ml/kg) can be given additionally until there is enough human milk. (39)
Counterfactual	Counterfactual exposure	NA	
	Counterfactual question	NA	
	Hypothesised outcome	NA	
	Further justification or suggested mechanism	NA	
	Reverse counterfactual exposure	Risk of hypoglycaemia vs. no risk of hypoglycaemia	

	Reverse counterfactual question	How would the risk of hypoglycaemia affect the feeding method?	
	Reverse hypothesized outcome	We expect that newborns at risk of hypoglycaemia might be more likely to receive bottle feeding.	
	Further justification or suggested mechanism	Bottle feeding allows a consistent, controlled intake of formula (glucose) which enables better monitoring.	
Conclusion	Reverse		

Edge ID (27)	Variable From	Variable To	Assessed Prior
Variable	Risk of hypoglycaemia	Healthy newborn	No
Measurement	Feeding intervention to prevent hypoglycaemia	Measured bilirubin values, temperatures, glucose values from surveillance curve + Movement data for transfer	
	Question	Answer (Y/N)	Notes
Temporality	Hypothesised direction	Yes	Risk of hypoglycaemia precedes determination of newborn's health status
	Reverse direction	No	
Face-validity	Hypothesised direction	Yes	Risk of hypoglycaemia influences the newborns' health
	Reverse direction	No	
Recourse to theory	Hypothesised direction	Yes	One goal of managing neonatal hypoglycaemia is to correct blood glucose level (36) which contributes to the newborn's health.

	Reverse direction	No	Healthy term newborns do not develop symptomatic hypoglycaemia as a result of simple underfeeding (40)
Counterfactual	Counterfactual exposure	Risk of hypoglycaemia vs. no risk of hypoglycaemia	
	Counterfactual question	How would the risk of hypoglycaemia affect the newborns health status?	
	Hypothesised outcome	We expect that newborns with risk of hypoglycaemia are more likely to develop hypoglycaemia.	
	Further justification or suggested mechanism	NA	
	Reverse counterfactual exposure	NA	
	Reverse counterfactual question	NA	
	Reverse hypothesized outcome	NA	
	Further justification or suggested mechanism	NA	
Conclusion	Retain		

Edge ID (28)	Variable From	Variable To	Assessed Prior
Variable	Cold season	Risk of hypothermia	No
Measurement	Average temperature during hospital stay	No measurement available	
	Question	Answer (Y/N)	Notes
Temporality	Hypothesised direction	Yes	Temperature in hospital exists before birth of newborn and its risk of hypothermia

	Reverse direction	No	
Face-validity	Hypothesised direction	Yes	It is plausible that cold temperatures increase the risk of hypothermia
	Reverse direction	No	
Recourse to theory	Hypothesised direction	Yes	Newborns who were born in delivery room $\leq 27.5^{\circ}\text{C}$ had a OR 3.54, 95% CI [2.43–5.14] $p < 0.001$ of developing hypothermia. Newborns in postpartum room with temperature $\leq 27.5^{\circ}\text{C}$ had a OR 1.91, 95% CI [1.30–2.82] $p < 0.001$ of developing hypothermia. (30) Risk of moderate or severe hypothermia increased by 41.3% (95% CI, [40.0%–42.7%] for every 5°C decrease in average ambient temperature. Relative to the highest quintile, risk was 4.03 (95% CI [3.77–4.30 times higher among babies exposed to the lowest quintile of average ambient temperature. (41)
	Reverse direction	No	
Counterfactual	Counterfactual exposure	Different seasonal temperatures, e.g. summer vs. winter	
	Counterfactual question	How would the risk of hypothermia in newborns differ	

		between summer and winter?	
	Hypothesised outcome	We expect a higher risk of hypothermia in winter.	
	Further justification or suggested mechanism	NA	
	Reverse counterfactual exposure	NA	
	Reverse counterfactual question	NA	
	Reverse hypothesized outcome	NA	
	Further justification or suggested mechanism	NA	
	Conclusion	Retain	

Edge ID (29)	Variable From	Variable To	Assessed Prior
Variable	Time of birth	Risk of hypothermia	No
Measurement	Time of birth	No measurement available	
	Question	Answer (Y/N)	Notes
Temporality	Hypothesised direction	Yes	Time of birth precedes risk of hypothermia
	Reverse direction	No	
Face-validity	Hypothesised direction	Yes	It is plausible that newborns who are born in nighttime might be at higher risk of hypothermia due to colder temperatures and reduced staffing
	Reverse direction	No	
Recourse to theory	Hypothesised direction	Yes	Newborns who were born between 1AM and 6.59 AM were more likely to develop moderate/severe hypothermia (OR 1.20, 95% CI [1.00–1.44] (19)

	Reverse direction	No	
Counterfactual	Counterfactual exposure	Births on different times of the day, e.g. daytime vs. nighttime	
	Counterfactual question	Would the risk of hypothermia in newborns differ if births occurred during different times of the day?	
	Hypothesised outcome	We expect there would be more newborns at risk of hypothermia in the nighttime.	
	Further justification or suggested mechanism	Due to lower ambient temperatures and potential reduced staffing.	
	Reverse counterfactual exposure	NA	
	Reverse counterfactual question	NA	
	Reverse hypothesized outcome	NA	
	Further justification or suggested mechanism	NA	
Conclusion	Delete		Association is likely mediated by staffing, this edge and the node are deleted.

Edge ID (30)	Variable From	Variable To	Assessed Prior
Variable	Risk of hypothermia	Healthy newborn	No
Measurement	No measurement available	Measured bilirubin values, temperatures, glucose values from surveillance curve + Movement data for transfer	
	Question	Answer (Y/N)	Notes
Temporality	Hypothesised direction	Yes	Risk of hypothermia occurs before

			determining if a newborn is healthy
	Reverse direction	No	
Face-validity	Hypothesised direction	Yes	It is plausible that preventing hypothermia is crucial for maintaining a newborn healthy
	Reverse direction	No	
Recourse to theory	Hypothesised direction	Yes	Hypothermia is an independent predictor of neonatal morbidity and mortality. (3)
	Reverse direction	No	
Counterfactual	Counterfactual exposure	Risk of hypothermia vs. no risk of hypothermia	
	Counterfactual question	How would the risk of hypothermia affect the status of a healthy newborn?	
	Hypothesised outcome	We expect that more newborns would have hypothermia when they all have a risk of hypothermia.	
	Further justification or suggested mechanism	A stable body temperature is essential for physiological functions and overall health in newborns.	
	Reverse counterfactual exposure	NA	
	Reverse counterfactual question	NA	
	Reverse hypothesized outcome	NA	
	Further justification or suggested mechanism	NA	
Conclusion	Retain		

Edge ID (31)

	Variable From	Variable To	Assessed Prior
Variable	Feeding method (Breastfeeding/Bottle)	Staffing exposure (postnatal unit)	No
Measurement	Feeding entries from EHR to define breastfeeding, bottle feeding or mixed.	Proportion of target nurse-to-patient ratio during hospital stay on postnatal unit.	
	Question	Answer (Y/N)	Notes
Temporality	Hypothesised direction	Yes	Feeding method precedes staffing exposure on postnatal unit as newborn has already been fed in delivery room
	Reverse direction	No	Staffing exposure on postnatal unit cannot influence decision on feeding method in labour ward.
Face-validity	Hypothesised direction	Yes	Guidance in breastfeeding is time-consuming and influences staffing exposure on postnatal unit
	Reverse direction	No	
Recourse to theory	Hypothesised direction	Yes	Breastfeeding on postnatal ward needs guidance, education and hands-on assistance from staff. Challenges can arise, such as difficulties with latching, feeding techniques, and ensuring adequate milk supply (21) which are time-consuming and influence staff on postnatal ward.
	Reverse direction	No	

	Counterfactual	Counterfactual exposure	Different feeding methods on postnatal unit; e.g. breastfeeding vs. bottle feeding	
		Counterfactual question	How would different feeding methods affect the staffing exposure on postnatal unit?	
		Hypothesised outcome	We expect there would be a higher staffing needs if all newborns were breastfed.	
		Further justification or suggested mechanism	Support in breastfeeding is time-consuming	
		Reverse counterfactual exposure	NA	
		Reverse counterfactual question	NA	
		Reverse hypothesized outcome	NA	
		Further justification or suggested mechanism	NA	
	Conclusion	Retain		

Edge ID (32)	Variable From	Variable To	Assessed Prior
Variable	Feeding method (Breastfeeding/Bottle)	Risk of hypothermia	No
Measurement	Feeding entries from EHR to define breastfeeding, bottle feeding or mixed.	No measurement available	
	Question	Answer (Y/N)	Notes
Temporality	Hypothesised direction	Yes	Feeding method precedes risk of hypothermia
	Reverse direction	Yes	Risk of hypothermia may precede feeding method
Face-validity	Hypothesised direction	Yes	It is plausible that feeding method, e.g. breastfeeding, may

			prevent hypothermia in newborns
	Reverse direction	No	Hypothermia is not a reason to change feeding method
Recourse to theory	Hypothesised direction	Yes	Bottle only fed newborns were at higher risk of developing moderate/severe hypothermia (OR 1.53, 95% CI [1.32–1.77] (19))
	Reverse direction	No	
Counterfactual	Counterfactual exposure	Different feeding methods on postnatal unit; e.g. breastfeeding vs. bottle feeding	
	Counterfactual question	How would different feeding methods affect the risk of hypothermia?	
	Hypothesised outcome	We expect there would be a higher risk of hypothermia if all newborns were bottle-fed.	
	Further justification or suggested mechanism	NA	
	Reverse counterfactual exposure	NA	
	Reverse counterfactual question	NA	
	Reverse hypothesized outcome	NA	
	Further justification or suggested mechanism	NA	
Conclusion	Retain		

Edge ID (33)	Variable From	Variable To	Assessed Prior
Variable	Feeding method (Breastfeeding/Bottle)	Risk of hyperbilirubinaemia	No
Measurement	Feeding entries from EHR to define	Measured bilirubin values,	

	breastfeeding, bottle feeding or mixed.	temperatures, glucose values from surveillance curve + Movement data for transfer	
	Question	Answer (Y/N)	Notes
Temporality	Hypothesised direction	Yes	Feeding method occurs before development of possible hyperbilirubinaemia
	Reverse direction	No	Risk of hyperbilirubinaemia occurs after feeding method is determined
Face-validity	Hypothesised direction	Yes	It is plausible that feeding method affects bilirubin metabolism
	Reverse direction	No	
Recourse to theory	Hypothesised direction	Yes	A meta-analysis showed exclusive breastfeeding to be a risk factor of hyperbilirubinaemia OR =1.74, 95% CI [1.42– 2.12]. (43)
	Reverse direction	No	A sample of 17 hyperbilirubinaemic newborns (serum total bilirubin 17.8 ± 1.6 mg/dL) did not show significant differences in sucking parameters compared to control group (42) which might affect choice of feeding method.
Counterfactual	Counterfactual exposure	Different feeding methods on postnatal unit; e.g. breastfeeding vs. bottle feeding	
	Counterfactual question	How would different feeding methods	

			affect the risk of hyperbilirubinaemia?	
	Hypothesised outcome		We expect there would be a higher risk of hyperbilirubinaemia if all newborns were breastfed.	
	Further justification or suggested mechanism		Breastfed newborns may not receive sufficient breastmilk in the first days after birth which can lead to dehydration and increase bilirubin levels. Further they have decreased bowel movements as bilirubin is excreted with stool and some components of breastmilk might affect bilirubin metabolism.	
	Reverse counterfactual exposure		NA	
	Reverse counterfactual question		NA	
	Reverse hypothesized outcome		NA	
	Further justification or suggested mechanism		NA	
	Conclusion		Retain	

Edge ID (34)		Variable From	Variable To	Assessed Prior
	Variable	Risk of hyperbilirubinaemia	Healthy newborn	No
	Measurement	Measured bilirubin values, temperatures, glucose values from surveillance curve + Movement data for transfer	Measured bilirubin values, temperatures, glucose values from surveillance curve + Movement data for transfer	
		Question	Answer (Y/N)	Notes

Temporality	Hypothesised direction	Yes	Risk of hyperbilirubinaemia occurs before determining if a newborn is healthy
	Reverse direction	No	
Face-validity	Hypothesised direction	Yes	It is plausible that a higher risk of hyperbilirubinaemia could prevent a newborn from being classified as healthy
	Reverse direction	No	
Recourse to theory	Hypothesised direction	Yes	A high bilirubin level can lead to severe complications, including lifelong disability such as growth retardation, encephalopathy, autism and hearing impairment. (43)
	Reverse direction	No	
Counterfactual	Counterfactual exposure	Risk of hyperbilirubinaemia vs. no risk of hyperbilirubinaemia	
	Counterfactual question	How would the risk of hyperbilirubinaemia affect the health status of a healthy newborn?	
	Hypothesised outcome	We expect the risk of hyperbilirubinaemia would lead to more newborns with hyperbilirubinaemia.	
	Further justification or suggested mechanism	Untreated hyperbilirubinaemia can lead to encephalopathy and infections in newborns alongside lifelong disabilities.	
	Reverse counterfactual exposure	NA	
	Reverse counterfactual question	NA	

		Reverse hypothesized outcome	NA	
		Further justification or suggested mechanism	NA	
	Conclusion	Retain		

Edge ID (35)		Variable From	Variable To	Assessed Prior
	Variable	Staffing exposure (postnatal unit)	Risk of hypothermia	No
	Measurement	Proportion of target nurse-to-patient ratio during hospital stay on postnatal unit.	No measurement available	
		Question	Answer (Y/N)	Notes
	Temporality	Hypothesised direction	Yes	Staffing levels on postnatal unit can influence health outcomes of newborns
		Reverse direction	No	
	Face-validity	Hypothesised direction	Yes	It is plausible that high staffing levels contribute to better care and thus healthier newborns
		Reverse direction	No	
	Recourse to theory	Hypothesised direction	Yes	Nurses were worried about bad outcomes for the baby due to less frequent assessments in the context of being too busy (1) Nursing interventions to achieve normal body temperature in newborns may include environmental temperature 23–25 °C, use of radiant warmers, exothermic

			mattresses, woollen or plastic caps, plastic wraps, humidified and heated gases (3). Those interventions cannot be ensured with low proportion of target nurse-to-patient ratio.
	Reverse direction	No	
Counterfactual	Counterfactual exposure	Low vs. high proportion of target nurse-to-patient ratio during hospital stay on postnatal unit	
	Counterfactual question	What is the effect of low vs. high proportion of target nurse-to-patient ratio during hospital stay on postnatal unit on risk of hypothermia of newborns?	
	Hypothesised outcome	We expect that higher nurse-to-patient ratios would be associated with better newborn health outcomes.	
	Further justification or suggested mechanism	High staffing levels enhance thorough monitoring of temperature, glucose and bilirubin and prompt reaction in case of abnormalities which contribute to newborn's health	
	Reverse counterfactual exposure	NA	
	Reverse counterfactual question	NA	
	Reverse hypothesized outcome	NA	
	Further justification or suggested mechanism	NA	
Conclusion	Retain		

Edge ID (36)

	Variable From	Variable To	Assessed Prior
Variable	Gestational age	Risk of hypoglycaemia	No
Measurement	Duration of pregnancy in days (from BFS data)	Feeding intervention to prevent hypoglycaemia	
	Question	Answer (Y/N)	Notes
Temporality	Hypothesised direction	Yes	Gestational age is determined before birth and can influence the risk of hypoglycaemia
	Reverse direction	No	
Face-validity	Hypothesised direction	Yes	It is plausible that low gestational age is associated with hypoglycaemia due to immature function of glucose metabolism
	Reverse direction	No	
Recourse to theory	Hypothesised direction	Yes	Gestational week is a protective factor for neonatal hypoglycaemia (OR=0.80, 95% CI [0.66 – 0.96] (44))
	Reverse direction	No	
Counterfactual	Counterfactual exposure	Different gestational ages, e.g. 36+0 weeks vs. 40+0 weeks	
	Counterfactual question	How would different gestational ages affect the risk of hypoglycaemia?	
	Hypothesised outcome	We expect there would be a higher rate of hypoglycaemia in late preterms (36+0 weeks).	
	Further justification or suggested mechanism	Preterm newborns have lower	

			glycogen store and immature liver function which makes them prone to hypoglycaemia	
		Reverse counterfactual exposure	NA	
		Reverse counterfactual question	NA	
		Reverse hypothesized outcome	NA	
		Further justification or suggested mechanism	NA	
	Conclusion	Retain		

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